

Generations and Gender Survey (Round II)

Working Paper

Intended, ideal, and actual fertility in 11 European countries. Evidence on fertility gaps in different age groups from the Generations and Gender Survey

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Please cite as: Friedrich, C. & Bujard, M. (2025). Intended, ideal, and actual fertility in 11 European countries. Evidence on fertility gaps in different age groups from the Generations and Gender Survey. Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17092718

Intended, ideal, and actual fertility in 11 European countries. Evidence on fertility gaps in different age groups from the Generations and Gender Survey

Carmen Friedrich¹ and Martin Bujard^{1,2}

Abstract

In low-fertility contexts, previous research shows a persistent gap between actual and desired or intended family size. Understanding discrepancies between fertility ideals, intentions, and behaviour is highly relevant, as this provides invaluable insights into the age-specific mechanisms that govern the realisation (or non-realisation) of individuals' intended or desired family size. Using novel data of eleven European countries from the Generations and Gender Survey, collected during and after the COVID-19 pandemic (2020-2023), we compared ideal, intended, and actual fertility for women aged 18-49. We calculated two fertility gaps among women in different age-groups and, for the first time, analysed these gaps as dependent variables using linear regression models. We examined how socio-demographic factors are linked to the intended number of children among women aged 18-29, the fertility gap to intentions among women aged 30-39, and the fertility gap to ideals among women aged 40-49. The results indicate the intended family size for ages 18-29 ranges from 1.82 (Finland) to 2.47 (Moldova). The gap between women's mean ideal and actual family size (40-49) ranges from 0.42 to 0.63 across countries. The multivariable analyses reveal similar country patterns: Religiosity particularly matters for intended fertility early in the reproductive life course, while education plays a role in the primary phase of family formation. Moreover, all models confirm the high relevance of partnership status. Since fertility intentions are significantly higher than period fertility, this suggests that the early 2020s fertility decline could have been driven by uncertainty and – as a consequence – a postponement of childbirth.

Keywords: Fertility, Child intentions, Ideal number of children, Fertility gap, Cross-country comparison, Uncertainty

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1 Introduction

In the aftermath of the global Covid-19 pandemic, fertility in Europe reached historically low levels, with the average Total Fertility Rate (TFR) across the European Union (EU) reaching 1.38 in 2023 (Eurostat, 2025). This figure stands even below the previous low recorded in the early 2000s. While the low levels in the early 2000s, which were partly attributed to the timing of childbearing (Sobotka, 2004; Goldstein et al., 2009), were superseded in the 2010s by EU-TFR between 1.5 and 1.6, the decline in the early 2020s was attributed to vaccine-related postponement and uncertainties (Bujard & Andersson, 2024; Winkler-Dworak et al., 2024). During this second phase of decline, even some Northern European countries reached unprecedentedly low fertility rates, with some dropping below 1.5. Against this backdrop, it is crucial to know whether period fertility trends stem from timing effects or reflect potential changes in future plans, particularly when looking at the fertility intentions and ideals of the young generation, which are of substantial predictive value (Gietel-Basten et al., 2024). This can help in assessing whether the recent decline is temporary – mainly due to fertility postponement that may be followed, at least in part, by recuperation – and whether birth rates will stabilise again at levels from before the onset of the polycrisis (Lawrence et al., 2024; Kriechel et al., 2024) or if it will lead to a permanent fertility decline.

However, the majority of research on fertility intentions and ideals is based on data collected well before the recent fertility decline. A great variety of literature exists on hypothetical fertility indicators (Philipov & Bernardi, 2012), such as fertility intentions or fertility ideals, measured by the Eurobarometer (Sobotka & Beaujouan, 2014; Testa, 2012, Sobotka & Lutz, 2010), the Fertility and Family Survey (Beaujouan & Berghammer, 2019), or the first round of data collection of the Generation and Gender Survey (GGS-I) (Brzozowska & Beaujouan, 2021; Harknett & Hartnett, 2014). The findings of this research indicate that the mean intended and ideal number of children in Europe remains near or above replacement level. However, it should be noted that the majority of these data were collected mainly in the 1990s, 2000s, or shortly thereafter – well before the onset of the current decline. For more recent data, which are comparable for many European countries (for three countries see: Krapf et al. 2023), the new data collection of the GGS (GGS-II, see Gauthier et al., 2023; Gauthier et al., 2022) allows for analysing recent trends in fertility ideals and intentions.

In order to compare hypothetical and real fertility indicators, many scholars describe a fertility gap, which is defined as the difference between hypothetical and realised fertility (Philipov & Bernardi, 2012; Sobotka & Lutz, 2010). In this regard, the distinction between fertility ideals and fertility intentions is crucial. Personal fertility ideals are operationalised as for the best conditions of life and fertility intentions for the specific situation of women or men regarding health, partnership, housing,

and occupation. Both ideals and intentions can be interpreted based on Miller's theory (Miller, 2011; Miller & Pasta, 1995a), whereby desires correspond to ideals (Philipov & Bernardi, 2012). Consequently, the fertility gap should be further categorised into two distinct components: (a) an intended-actual fertility gap, which quantifies the difference between actual and intended fertility (Beaujouan & Berghammer, 2019), and (b) an ideal-actual fertility gap, which measures the difference between actual and desired fertility (Testa, 2012). While existing literature often focuses on the fertility gap of completed fertility (Beaujouan & Berghammer, 2019, Sobotka & Lutz, 2010), the age-specific process of postponement and recuperation (Sobotka, 2004, Sobotka et al., 2012) has not yet been analytically linked to fertility intentions or ideals. To the best of our knowledge, age-specific fertility gaps have not yet been analysed as a dependent variable. Furthermore, a systematic and up-to-date empirical comparison between fertility ideals and fertility intentions in relation to actual fertility and the respective fertility gaps for different age groups is missing. Up-to-date knowledge on the extent of discrepancies between ideals, intentions, and behaviour regarding fertility is highly relevant, as it provides insights into age-specific mechanisms that influence the realisation of intended or desired family sizes. The cross-national approach facilitates the exploration of variations in fertility gaps and the identification of potential individual socio-demographic determinants for realising fertility intentions and ideals that differ by country.

This study contributes to the existing literature in three ways: First, we compare child-number intentions and ideals held by individuals with their actual number of children for a selection of eleven European countries (Austria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Germany, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, United Kingdom) as measured in early 2020. With this comprehensive overview of the data, we set out to explore whether changes in fertility ideals or intentions within specific age groups help to explain the recent decline in fertility rates. Second, we contribute to the existing literature by identifying patterns in fertility ideals, fertility intentions, and actual fertility in a cross-sectional design for women aged 18-49 years. This allows us to illuminate the fertility gap over the life course, in particular postponement and recuperation patterns. In pursuit of this objective, we calculated two different kinds of fertility gaps (the intended-actual fertility gap and the ideal-actual fertility gap) for different age groups. Third, this paper is – to the best of our knowledge – the first to analyse both fertility gaps as dependent variables for specific age ranges. With multivariable analyses, we illuminate how fertility intentions and fertility gaps are influenced by specific socio-demographic characteristics. Thereby, we focus on fertility intentions among young women at the beginning of their reproductive life course. Fertility intentions evolve over time, therefore, an examination of the association between socio-demographic characteristics and the intended number of children among a sample of young women provides insights into the relationship between these factors and lifetime fertility intentions, before they are significantly shaped by life events and constraints. This will be

complemented by analyses of the intended-actual fertility gap during the primary phase of family formation, with the main objective to shed light on factors related to fertility postponement. Finally, we explore the ideal-actual fertility gap at the end of the reproductive life course, a topic of particular interest at this life stage as it reveals the gap to the “true” reproductive goal and the personal characteristics linked to (un)realised fertility preferences over the entire preceding life course. These analyses are relevant to both macro- and micro-level fertility patterns: At the macro-level, the analysis of these fertility gaps facilitates a more comprehensive understanding of the current low and lowest-low fertility in Europe. At the individual-level, fertility gaps that remain unclosed over the life course can be indicative of a failed life transition (Loftus & Andriot, 2012) and often necessitate a psychological adjustment of life goals (Brandtstädter & Rothermund, 2002).

The structure of the paper is as follows: After giving an overview on the concepts of ideal and intended fertility and previous research on aggregate fertility gaps, we describe the data used and our analytical approach. In the results section, we present hypothetical and real fertility indicators for women across eleven European countries, and we provide descriptive statistics for two distinct fertility gaps (intended-actual, ideal-actual) among women of reproductive age (18-49). We then present results from Poisson regression models for the intended family size of young women (18-29), and from linear regression models for the gap between intended and actual fertility (women aged 30-39), and the gap between ideal and actual fertility (women aged 40-49). In conclusion, we discuss the results of the study in the context of previous literature and reflect on their implications for the recent decline in birth rates.

2 Background

2.1 Hypothetical fertility indicators and fertility gaps

There are various indicators to measure hypothetical fertility, and in this context, it is crucial to draw a distinction between intended and ideal fertility. Fertility intentions can be defined as concrete fertility goals that can be operationalised for a specific period (for example, three years in the GGS, following the “Theory of Planned Behavior” (Ajzen, 2012)) or for the course of an individual’s reproductive life. The concept of fertility ideals can be understood as societal norms or personal ideals, depending on the manner in which the survey question is phrased: Personal fertility ideals represent an individual’s desire, while societal norms regarding fertility pertain to the entire society (Testa, 2012). In this study, we focus on the personal child-number ideals and individuals’ life time child-

number intentions. The personal ideal number of children “when operationalised to refer to best conditions of life, measures fertility desires as defined in socio-psychological theories” (Philipov & Bernardi, 2012: 496). In this case, the terms “personal ideal number of children” and “desired number of children” are used to refer to the same concept.

Hypothetical fertility can change over the course of an individual’s life. This is especially true for fertility intentions, as, in contrast to fertility ideals, the intended number of children takes potential situational constraints into account and is adjusted according to the personal circumstances of the individual (Miller, 2011). This phenomenon could be attributed to various factors, including the awareness of the “biological clock” for childbearing (Wagner et al., 2019), partnership changes (Iacovou & Tavares, 2011), or educational and occupational career experiences (Liefbroer, 2009). Based on this understanding, fertility intentions are the intermediate step between fertility desires and fertility behaviour (Miller & Pasta, 1995a). This also means that an individual’s fertility gap between the intended and actual number of children (fertility gap to intentions) is likely to be smaller than the gap between the personal ideal and actual number of children (fertility gap to ideals), as intended fertility is likely to be already adjusted to reality – especially by the end of the reproductive years. On the other hand, the fertility gap to personal ideals, reflects the difference between the family size that individuals aspire to have, irrespective of any constraints, and their actual number of children. Nevertheless, there is evidence to suggest that fertility ideals are not entirely immune to adjustments: While they appear to be less influenced by short-term changes in life circumstances, the ideal number of children may still undergo revision if individuals come to perceive their desires as unlikely to be fulfilled, for instance as a result of advancing age (Kuhnt et al., 2017; Gray et al., 2013). Furthermore, the literature has demonstrated that there is a tendency for fertility ideals to undergo modification after the birth of a(n) (additional) child (Heiland et al., 2008; Miller & Pasta, 1995b).

From a life course perspective, both fertility gaps (to intentions and to ideals) are likely to be large at the beginning of the reproductive life span. It is anticipated that during the primary phase of family formation, the fertility gap to intentions may begin to close. This could be either attributable to the realisation of childbearing intentions or to a downward adjustment of fertility intentions due to personal constraints or life circumstances. In contrast, the gap between the ideal number of children and the actual number of children is expected to remain larger than the fertility gap to intentions, as personal ideal fertility is likely to be more stable over the life course. By the end of the reproductive life span, the gap between the intended and actual number of children might close, while a gap to fertility ideals is likely to remain. A (large) gap between the intended and actual number of children can be attributed to two main factors: namely, the postponement of childbirth (Mills et al., 2011) or unequal childbearing opportunities (Beaujouan, 2023). There is extensive literature on the socio-

demographic differences in actual, intended, and ideal fertility, as well as in the realisation of (short-term) fertility intentions. Key factors include education (e.g., Krapf et al., 2023; Vasireddy et al., 2023), economic uncertainty (such as unemployment or the perception of the individual's economic situation, e.g., Kreyenfeld, 2015; Vignoli et al., 2020), religiosity (e.g., Buber-Ennsner & Berghammer, 2021; Bein et al., 2023), infertility (e.g., Greil et al., 2024), partnership status (e.g., Sturm et al., 2023; Iacovou & Tavares, 2011; Liefbroer, 2009), and migration background (e.g., Kulu et al., 2019; Milewski & Mussino, 2019). However, to the best of our knowledge, there is no research that analyses individuals' fertility gap to intentions and fertility gap to personal ideals as dependent variables. In our multivariate analyses, we estimated the association between several of the key factors identified in the literature and fertility intentions among young women at the beginning of their reproductive life course, the fertility gap to intentions during the primary phase of family formation and the fertility gap to personal ideals at the end of the reproductive life course.

2.2 Previous research on aggregate fertility gaps

In many countries with low fertility rates, previous research has shown an aggregate gap at the country level between ideal fertility or fertility intentions and behaviour (e.g., Beaujouan & Berghammer, 2019; Sobotka & Lutz, 2010). Many studies compare the intended or ideal fertility with period indicators of fertility (Adserà, 2006; Bongaarts, 2008; Lutz, 2007; Sobotka & Lutz, 2010; Testa, 2012). Other studies use a cohort approach by comparing stated fertility desires or intentions in early adulthood with completed cohort fertility (Beaujouan & Berghammer, 2019; Berrington & Patarro, 2014; Freedman et al., 1980; Gietel-Basten et al., 2024; Morgan & Rackin, 2010; Noack & Ostby, 2002; Smallwood & Jefferies, 2003).

Only a few scholars have compared fertility preferences of young women (or men) with completed cohort fertility. Gietel-Basten et al. (2024) found a strong relationship between women's ideal and actual fertility across 46 developing countries and the United States, despite a two-decade time interval between survey responses and the measurement of completed cohort fertility. Also using a cohort approach, Beaujouan & Berghammer (2019) show that the mean intended family size of young women aged 20-24 and born in the early 1970s in Europe and the United States exceeds the completed total fertility rate of the same cohort. This finding indicates that a significant proportion of women did not fully realise the number of children they intended to have in early adulthood. However, considerable disparities in this cohort's intended-actual fertility gap are evident across different countries, varying from around 0.1 children per woman in the US and France to more than 0.6 children per woman in Southern European countries. Relatively large fertility gaps were also found in the Baltic States and Slovenia, whereas other countries in the Central and Eastern European countries display

smaller gaps (Czech Republic, Bulgaria, and Hungary). In German-speaking countries, the findings revealed moderate fertility gaps in Austria and Germany, and a large gap in Switzerland, where fertility intentions were much higher. In Norway and the Netherlands, large fertility gaps can also be explained by relatively high fertility intentions in early adulthood.

Focusing on fertility intentions over a three-year time period rather than lifetime intentions, Harknett & Hartnett (2014) demonstrated for 20 out of 22 European countries in the 2004 and 2007 European Social Survey that the proportion of women with short-term fertility intentions exceeded the proportion of women who gave birth in the following three years. For the majority of countries, the “aggregate fertility achievement rate” ranged between 50% and 70%, which means that for every 100 births intended, between 50 and 70 births were realised. The lowest rates (ranging from 32% and 44%) were found in Southern Europe, Switzerland, and Austria.

Testa (2012) analysed 27 European countries using data from the 2011 Eurobarometer Survey and showed that men and women aged 55 and over in 2011 would have preferred to have had, respectively, on average 0.2 and 0.3 more children than they actually had. For women and men aged 40-54 the ideal-actual fertility gap was, on average, 0.4 and 0.5, respectively. The values ranged from 0.1 (Malta) to 0.8 (Sweden) among women and from 0.1 (eastern Germany) to 1.0 (Greece) among men.

In the studies concerning aggregate fertility gaps, the focus is often on the gap to the final number of children, and the data on which these studies are based are typically from the 1990s and early 2000s. Our contribution to the literature is, first of all, the use of recent data to provide a comprehensive and up-to-date cross-country comparison of hypothetical fertility indicators and actual fertility rates. In addition, we present two different fertility gaps across various age groups and their underlying factors.

3 Method

3.1 Data and sample

Using data from the Generations and Gender Survey round 2 (GGS-II, Gauthier et al. 2023; Gauthier et al. 2022), collected between 2020 and 2022, we examined the intended, ideal, and actual number of children for women by age for eleven European countries (Austria (Neuwirth et al., 2024), Croatia, Czech Republic (Kreidl et al., 2023), Denmark (Fallesen et al., 2021), Estonia (Puur et al., 2023), Finland (Berg et al., 2023), Germany (Bujard et al., 2024; Bujard et al., 2025), Moldova (Republic of Moldova -

Generations and Gender Survey, 2020), Netherlands, Norway (Dommermuth et al., 2020), United Kingdom (Perelli-Harris et al., 2023)). These are all the European countries for which data were available at the time of writing, except for Belarus, Kazakhstan, and Sweden, where information on intended and/or ideal fertility was not collected. The GGS is an international comparative panel study that collects nationally representative data on life-course and family dynamics. In the majority of countries, the GGS-II was conducted exclusively via web-based questionnaires (CAWI). In the Czech Republic, CAWI was combined with computer-assisted personal interviews (CAPI), while in Germany, it was supplemented with paper-and-pencil interviewing (PAPI). In Moldova, the survey was conducted exclusively through CAPI.

The analytic sample for the descriptive analyses is restricted to women aged 18-49 who have no missing information on the intended, ideal, and actual number of children (see Table 1 for country sample sizes). The lower age limit is determined by the target population of the GGS-II, which includes individuals starting at age 18. The upper age limit corresponds to the age at which fertility researchers generally consider reproductive age to end. The age ranges of the GGS target populations vary by country, with some extending up to 79, while all countries encompass the age range of 18 to 49. For the multivariate analyses, we used three different age ranges varying according to the variable of interest: 18-29 for the analysis of the intended number of children (beginning of the reproductive life course), 30-39 for the analysis of the intended-actual fertility gap (primary phase of family formation), and 40-49 for the analysis of the ideal-actual fertility gap (end of the reproductive life course). Excluding women with missing information on the hypothetical fertility indicators also means excluding those who express uncertainty by selecting the “don’t know” response option. This share is by no means negligible: Among women aged 18-49, it ranges from 17% to 35% for the intended number of children and from 5% to 16% for the ideal number of children. It is noteworthy that in Moldova, this share is particularly low for both indicators, at 4% and 2%, respectively. This issue will be discussed in the last section.

3.2 Analytic strategy

In descriptive analyses, we display the mean children born, the mean intended number of children, and the mean ideal number of children by age for the eleven countries under study and show the differences in the two aggregate fertility gaps by age and country. It should be kept in mind that the women are not observed over a prolonged period of time, and therefore, the observed differences by age do not necessarily reflect changes over the life course, but merely serve as an approximation of such changes. For the descriptive analyses, weights adjust for biases in various socio-demographic variables (see note of Table 1 for details on country-specific weights). The actual number of children is

defined as the total number of all biological children reported by the respondents, whether with a current or previous partner or out of cohabitation. In the GGS-II, all respondents were asked about their ideal number of children (“For you personally, what would be the ideal number of children you would like to have or would have liked to have had?”). In the event that respondents expressed an intention to have (further) children, they were asked to report their intended family size (“How many (more) children – including biological and adoptive children – do you intend to have overall? [Not including existing children]”). We calculated the overall intended number of children by adding the number of children born to the (further) intended number of children reported in response to this question. Finally, we constructed two fertility gaps: (1) The intended-actual fertility gap, which was calculated by subtracting the actual number of children from the intended number of children, and (2) the ideal-actual fertility gap, which was calculated by subtracting the actual number of children from the ideal number of children.

In a second step, we estimated three models for each country for specific age groups with the following dependent variables: (1) the intended number of children among women aged 18-29, (2) the fertility gap between the intended and realised number of children among women aged 30-39, and (3) the fertility gap between the ideal family size and children ever born among women aged 40-49. We used Poisson regression models for the intended family size and linear regression models for the fertility gaps. In all models, we used robust standard errors and included several socio-demographic variables: age, the level of education using the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED-11, low (ISCED 0-2), middle (ISCED 3-4), high (ISCED 5-8)), religiosity and whether the woman was born in the country of survey or elsewhere. In the GGS-II, respondents were asked to express their religiosity on a scale from 0 (not at all religious) to 10 (very religious), irrespective of their affiliation to a specific religion. We distinguish between low (0-2), medium (3-8), and high (9-10) religiosity, as has been done in previous studies (e.g., Buber-Enns et al. 2018, Krapf et al. 2023). The models incorporating the intended number of children and the intended-actual fertility gap include additional variables: partnership status (no partner, cohabitation, married) and a measure of subjective economic uncertainty – specifically whether the woman believes her household can make ends meet financially (with great/some difficulty, fairly easy, (very) easily). The models on the ideal-actual fertility gap among women aged 40-49 do not include these two variables, as *current* economic uncertainty and partnership situation at the end of the reproductive phase are less relevant for the realisation of fertility ideals over the entire life course. Instead, a variable indicating whether the woman has ever been married is included. For each independent variable, we created a category to accommodate missing information. Thus, the multivariate analyses are based on the same sample as the descriptive analysis. As a robustness check, we estimated all models excluding individuals with missing data on any of the independent variables and the results remained similar. Table A1 in the appendix presents

the descriptive statistics for women aged 18-49 across all eleven countries, including actual, intended, and ideal fertility, as well as all independent variables used in the analysis.

4 Results

4.1 Descriptive analysis of fertility intentions, ideals, and fertility gaps

For all eleven countries under study, Figure 1 shows the mean number of children born, mean intended number of children, and mean ideal number of children by age. Table 1 additionally gives an overview of the two fertility gaps (mean intended-actual and ideal-actual), the mean gap between the ideal and intended number of children, and the mean actual, intended, and ideal number of children, all categorised by age groups and country.

On average, women have between 1.02 (Germany) and 1.60 (Moldova) children. In Moldova, women desire, on average, the largest families (2.68 children). Across all other countries, the mean ideal number of children ranges from 2.17 (Austria and Czech Republic) to 2.39 (Estonia). The number of children respondents actually intend to have is lower: In Germany, Austria, Netherlands, Czech Republic, and Finland the mean intended number of children is below 2.0. Respondents in Croatia, Estonia, Denmark, Norway and the United Kingdom intend to have, on average, close to or slightly more than two children. In Moldova, the mean intended number of children is highest (2.40).

Among young adults aged 18-29, the mean intended family size is relatively high. With 2.47, Moldova shows the highest rate, while the range in all other countries extends from 1.82 (Finland) to 2.18 (Croatia). When looking at the fertility gaps, we observe, as expected, that across all ages the aggregate gap to the number of children already born is greater for the ideal number of children than the intended number of children. As demonstrated in Figure 1, for all countries, the mean intended number of children and the mean number of children born are (nearly) equal at the end of women's childbearing years, suggesting that women adapt their intended number of children to their biological chances of having a child at older ages. In all countries except Moldova, women's mean intended-actual fertility gap is not above 0.1 in the age group 40-49. Overall, as women age, the intended number of children decreases, and as a consequence, the gap between the intended and ideal number of children widens. Regarding fertility desires, there is no clear downward adjustment to the actual number of children: Only in Germany, Moldova and the United Kingdom, the mean ideal number of

children decreases somewhat with age. For women aged 40-49, the gap between the mean ideal and actual family size ranges from 0.42 (Czech Republic) to 0.63 (Croatia) across countries.

For both German-speaking countries, Germany and Austria, we observe a relatively high mean intended-actual fertility gap for women aged 30-39 (0.60 and 0.67, respectively), along with a relatively low intended number of children (1.85 and 1.92, respectively). This finding suggests a high degree of birth postponement in these countries. In other countries with a similarly high gap (Norway, Denmark, Estonia, and the United Kingdom), the mean intended number of children is notably higher (close to or above two). In Moldova, postponement appears to be less pronounced, as women aged 30-39 have a fertility gap that is no higher than in most countries, despite having a high intended number of children.

Figure 1: Women’s actual, intended, and ideal number of children, by age and country, 2020-2023.

Source: GGS-II Germany (2021-2022), GGS-II Austria (2022-2023), GGS-II Netherlands (2022-2023), GGS-II, Czech Republic (2020-2022), GGS-II Croatia (2023), GGS-II Estonia (2021-2022), GGS-II Norway (2020), GGS-II Denmark (2021), GGS-II Finland (2021-2022), GGS-II Moldova (2020), GGS-II United Kingdom (2022-2023); three-year moving average, weighted data.

Table 1: Mean fertility gaps and mean actual, intended, and ideal number of children, by age group and country.

	Germany	Austria	Netherlands	Czech Republic	Croatia	Estonia	Norway	Denmark	Finland	Moldova	United Kingdom
Gap intended-actual fertility											
18-29	1.76	1.71	1.93	1.66	1.80	1.65	1.99	1.92	1.69	1.46	1.69
30-39	0.60	0.67	0.56	0.52	0.79	0.68	0.61	0.65	0.49	0.59	0.68
40-49	0.07	0.06	0.03	0.06	0.08	0.08	0.05	0.03	0.05	0.12	0.10
Total	0.80	0.80	0.85	0.66	0.85	0.73	0.93	0.96	0.72	0.80	0.87
Gap ideal-actual fertility											
18-29	2.16	1.89	2.07	1.79	1.95	1.78	2.20	2.10	1.95	1.62	1.98
30-39	1.07	0.96	0.81	0.74	1.00	0.84	0.88	1.04	0.81	0.86	0.85
40-49	0.59	0.46	0.49	0.42	0.63	0.51	0.44	0.54	0.54	0.59	0.62
Total	1.26	1.26	1.13	0.91	1.17	0.98	1.22	1.31	1.08	1.08	1.19
Gap ideal-intended fertility											
18-29	0.40	0.18	0.14	0.14	0.16	0.13	0.22	0.19	0.26	0.17	0.29
30-39	0.47	0.29	0.25	0.22	0.21	0.16	0.27	0.39	0.33	0.27	0.18
40-49	0.52	0.40	0.46	0.36	0.55	0.43	0.39	0.51	0.49	0.47	0.52
Total	0.46	0.46	0.28	0.25	0.33	0.25	0.29	0.35	0.36	0.28	0.32
Actual number of children											
18-29	0.23	0.27	0.14	0.28	0.39	0.46	0.18	0.18	0.13	1.01	0.41
30-39	1.24	1.25	1.32	1.39	1.39	1.53	1.48	1.33	1.29	1.93	1.35
40-49	1.55	1.70	1.74	1.87	1.77	2.01	1.94	1.83	1.81	1.97	1.67
Total	1.02	1.10	1.06	1.26	1.20	1.41	1.15	1.03	1.10	1.60	1.11
Intended number of children											
18-29	1.98	1.97	2.07	1.94	2.18	2.11	2.17	2.10	1.82	2.47	2.11
30-39	1.85	1.92	1.88	1.90	2.18	2.21	2.09	1.97	1.78	2.51	2.03
40-49	1.62	1.76	1.77	1.94	1.85	2.09	1.99	1.86	1.86	2.09	1.77
Total	1.82	1.88	1.91	1.92	2.05	2.14	2.09	1.99	1.82	2.40	1.98
Ideal number of children											
18-29	2.38	2.16	2.21	2.07	2.34	2.24	2.39	2.28	2.08	2.64	2.40
30-39	2.32	2.21	2.13	2.12	2.39	2.37	2.36	2.36	2.10	2.79	2.20
40-49	2.14	2.16	2.23	2.29	2.40	2.53	2.38	2.37	2.35	2.56	2.29
Total	2.28	2.17	2.19	2.17	2.38	2.39	2.38	2.34	2.18	2.68	2.30
Observations	9,533	2,634	2,410	1,794	2,256	2,806	1,922	3,420	1,224	2,234	2,713

Note: Weights adjust for various socio-demographic variables. Netherlands, Czech Republic, Croatia, Estonia, Norway, Denmark, Finland: age, sex, education, and region. Germany: age, sex, marital status, household size, employment status, education, migration background, population structure, place of residence (western/eastern Germany). Moldova: age and sex.

Source: GGS-II Germany (2021-2022), GGS-II Austria (2022-2023), GGS-II Netherlands (2022-2023), GGS-II Czech Republic (2020-2022), GGS-II Croatia (2023), GGS-II Estonia (2021-2022), GGS-II Norway (2020), GGS-II Denmark (2021), GGS-II Finland (2021-2022), GGS-II Moldova (2020), GGS-II United Kingdom (2022-2023).

4.2 Multivariable analyses on fertility intentions and age-specific fertility gaps

The results of the multivariate regression models are shown in Figures 2-4. Figure 2 presents the coefficient estimates of the Poisson regression models for the intended number of children of women aged 18-29. The coefficient estimates of the linear regression models for the fertility gap to intentions and the fertility gap to personal ideals of women aged 30-39 and 40-49, respectively, are shown in Figures 3 and 4.

Intended number of children, women aged 18-29

In all countries, the intended family size among young adults is not, or only very weakly, associated with age. The association is statistically significant only in Germany, Denmark, and Finland, where the coefficient is negative but close to zero. Thus, in these three countries, the intended number of children decreases very slightly with increasing age. Regarding education, we find statistically significant associations in only two countries: Germany, Denmark, and the United Kingdom. In Germany and Denmark, the intended number of children is lower among women with a low level of education than among women with a medium level of education, whereas in the United Kingdom, women with a low level of education report a higher intended number of children. We observe that married women intend to have more children than unmarried women, with substantial and statistically significant associations in nearly all countries. Furthermore, religiosity appears to be a relevant factor, with a higher degree of religiosity being associated with a higher intended number of children. The findings reveal a notable exception in Moldova, where no statistically significant associations are observed between intended fertility and either religiosity or union status. However, the coefficients have the same sign, with single women or women in non-marital cohabitation showing a slightly lower intended number of children than married women, and medium or high religious women demonstrating a slightly higher intended family size compared to low religious women. Statistically significant negative associations are only found in a very small number of countries for being foreign born (Czech Republic and Denmark) and subjective economic uncertainty (Czech Republic).

Fertility gap to intentions, women aged 30-39

The fertility gap to intentions among women in the primary phase of family formation is strongly associated with age. In all countries, the gap decreases with increasing age, and the association is statistically significant. Furthermore, a clear positive and statistically significant association between the gap and having a high level of education is evident in nearly all countries. Highly educated women show a larger gap than those with a medium level of education. Again, partnership status appears to be relevant in all countries. The statistically significant associations indicate that unmarried women

(single or in non-marital cohabitation) exhibit a larger gap between their intended and realised number of children compared to married women. The association with religiosity is less clear-cut, with statistically significant associations only observed in a number of countries: Germany, Austria, Czech Republic, Croatia, Estonia, and the United Kingdom. In these six countries, women with a higher degree of religiosity (medium and/or high religiosity) have a larger gap than women with a lower degree of religiosity. Similarly, for being foreign born, statistically significant associations are not found in all countries, with a positive association in Germany, Austria, the Netherlands, Croatia, Norway, Denmark, and the United Kingdom, and a negative association in the Czech Republic. For subjective economic uncertainty, the results show almost no statistically significant associations.

Fertility gap to personal ideals, women aged 40-49

No association with age can be seen for the fertility gap between ideal and realised number of children, except in Austria, where the gap slightly increases with increasing age. Regarding education, we find statistically significant associations in only a few countries: In Germany, the Netherlands, Croatia, and Estonia, highly educated women have a larger gap than women with a medium degree of education. In Austria, women with a low degree of education have a smaller gap than women with a medium degree of education. In all countries, women who have ever been married have a much smaller gap than women who are or were not married, and this association is statistically significant. For religiosity, statistically significant associations are only found in Germany, the Netherlands, the Czech Republic, Croatia, and Norway. In these five countries, the gap to personal ideals is more pronounced among women with a medium degree of religiosity than among women with a low degree of religiosity. A statistically significant association with being foreign born is found only in Austria and the United Kingdom, where first-generation migrant women have a larger gap between their ideal and realised family size than women born in the country.

Figure 2: Coefficient estimates from Poisson regression models with robust standard errors, dependent variable: intended number of children. Women aged 18-29.

Notes: Germany: n=2,961, Austria: n=837, Netherlands: n=791, Czech Republic: n=377, Croatia: n=719, Estonia: n=760, Norway: n=694, Denmark: n=1,350, Finland: n=448, Moldova: n=702, United Kingdom: n=810. 95% confidence intervals are displayed. Missing categories are not shown. Full regression tables are shown in the appendix in Table A2.

Source: GGS-II Germany (2021-2022), GGS-II Austria (2022-2023), GGS-II Netherlands (2022-2023), GGS-II Czech Republic (2020-2022), GGS-II Croatia (2023), GGS-II Estonia (2021-2022), GGS-II Norway (2020), GGS-II Denmark (2021), GGS-II Finland (2021-2022), GGS-II Moldova (2020), GGS-II United Kingdom (2022-2023).

Figure 3: Coefficient estimates from linear regression models with robust standard errors, dependent variable: intended-actual fertility gap. Women aged 30-39.

Notes: Germany: n=3,492, Austria: n=833, Netherlands: n=822, Czech Republic: n=684, Croatia: n=644, Estonia: n=1,012, Norway: n=601, Denmark: n=994, Finland: n=432, Moldova: n=935, United Kingdom: n=1,006. 95% confidence intervals are displayed. Missing categories are not shown. Full regression tables are shown in the appendix in Table A3.

Source: GGS-II Germany (2021-2022), GGS-II Austria (2022-2023), GGS-II Netherlands (2022-2023), GGS-II Czech Republic (2020-2022), GGS-II Croatia (2023), GGS-II Estonia (2021-2022), GGS-II Norway (2020), GGS-II Denmark (2021), GGS-II Finland (2021-2022), GGS-II Moldova (2020), GGS-II United Kingdom (2022-2023).

Figure 4: Coefficient estimates from linear regression models with robust standard errors, dependent variable: ideal-actual fertility gap. Women aged 40-49.

Notes: Germany: n=3,074, Austria: n=964, Netherlands: n=797, Czech Republic: n=733, Croatia: n=893, Estonia: n=1,034, Norway: n=627, Denmark: n=1,076, Finland: n=344, Moldova: n=597, United Kingdom: n=897. 95% confidence intervals are displayed. Missing categories are not shown. Full regression tables are shown in the appendix in Table A4.
Source: GGS-II Germany (2021-2022), GGS-II Austria (2022-2023), GGS-II Netherlands (2022-2023), GGS-II Czech Republic (2020-2022), GGS-II Croatia (2023), GGS-II Estonia (2021-2022), GGS-II Norway (2020), GGS-II Denmark (2021), GGS-II Finland (2021-2022), GGS-II Moldova (2020), GGS-II United Kingdom (2022-2023).

5 Discussion

Based on newly available representative data from the second round of the Generations and Gender Survey (GGG-II), we gave a comprehensive overview of intended, ideal, and actual fertility for eleven European countries. The findings reveal that among younger generations, intended fertility is closely below or even above replacement level, while fertility ideals are even higher. By calculating two aggregate fertility gaps by age, namely (1) the gap between the intended number of children and children born (intended-actual fertility gap) and (2) the gap between the ideal number of children and children born (ideal-actual fertility gap), we linked fertility plans and norms with realised fertility during phases of life characterised by postponement and recuperation. We show that the two fertility gaps develop differently over the life course: Intentions and realised number of children converge in both directions between the ages 30 and 39, while the ideal number of children remains remarkably constant across the cross-sectional life course. Additionally, we examined how socio-demographic factors are linked to the intended number of children among young women at the beginning of their reproductive life course, the fertility gap to intentions during the primary phase of family formation, and the fertility gap to ideals at the end of the reproductive life course.

The fertility gap to personal ideals (the difference between personal ideals and actual fertility) ranges from 0.42 and 0.63 across countries for women aged 40-49, while their intentions are predominantly aligned with their actual fertility. The level of completed fertility is significantly below the established norms for women in their 40s. For women aged 30-39, we observed a fertility gap to personal intentions (the difference between intended and actual fertility) of 0.49-0.79. Using the age range 25-39, as in Testa (2012), the gap ranges from 0.70-1.05 – higher than the gap of 0.65-0.94 reported in Testa's study using data from 2011 for the seven countries that overlap with our sample (excluding Croatia, Moldova, and Norway). This indicates a tendency to postpone childbearing plans to a greater extent than was observed in 2011. In Northern European countries and the Netherlands, the fertility gap to personal ideals among women at the end of their reproductive life course in 2011 is very similar to what we observed. In contrast, the ideal-actual fertility gap in the German-speaking countries, Czech Republic, and the United Kingdom has increased since 2011, indicating once more a pronounced postponement of childbearing.

We found that the intended number of children among young women aged 18-29 ranges between 1.82 in Finland to 2.47 in Moldova. These relatively high fertility intentions of the younger generation indicate that the recent post-pandemic fertility decline in Europe does not signify a shift in fertility preferences (at least until 2022/2023). This decline may be attributed to the postponement of childbirth and the prevailing uncertainties. The multiple crises or polycrises, such as COVID-19, the

Russian war against Ukraine, and ongoing inflation, have created a climate of uncertainty which may be leading individuals to postpone childbearing. Economic crises have been shown to have an impact on fertility timing, such as economic recessions (e.g., Sobotka et al., 2011). Furthermore, current research suggests that rise of uncertainties about the future or “narratives of the future” influence short-term fertility intentions and childbearing behaviour (Vignoli et al., 2020, 2022). However, the fertility preferences of young people have been shown to have a remarkable predictive value for completed fertility (Gietel-Basten et al. 2024). Further research is required to determine whether fertility intentions have declined in more recent years or will do so in the near future, particularly using longitudinal studies to examine changes in fertility intentions. When data from the second wave of the GGS-II become available, it will allow for a comparison between the 2020-2023 data used in this study and data from approximately 2024-2026. It is important to note that while the fertility intentions of young women are higher than the current period fertility rates, they are lower than those of young women in the 1990s. Seven countries – Austria, Czech Republic, Estonia, Germany, Netherlands, Norway and the United Kingdom – were also analysed by Beaujouan and Berghammer (2019). In all these countries, except for the German-speaking ones, the mean intended number of children among women aged 20-24 in the 1990s exceeded 2.0 and surpasses the numbers observed in our data from 2020-2023. A similar pattern is evident – again with the exception of Germany and Austria – when comparing it to the mean fertility intentions of young women (aged 15-24) in 2011 (Testa, 2012).

Multivariable analyses have revealed that educational attainment plays a role primarily in the family formation phase. This is consistent with previous research, showing that women with higher levels of education tend to postpone childbirth (Kravdal & Rindfuss, 2008; Nicoletti & Tanturri, 2008). Furthermore, all models confirm the strong relevance of partnership status for both fertility intentions at a younger age and fertility gaps. This finding aligns with previous research showing that having a partner has a positive influence on fertility intentions (Sturm et al., 2023) and the observation that, in European countries, the most prevalent reason for unmet fertility intentions is the absence of a suitable partner (Testa, 2007). Religiosity appears to shape the intended number of children, particularly during the early stages in life. This result is consistent with the findings of a recent study using German panel data, which demonstrated that religiosity primarily influences fertility intentions during the teenage years, but has minimal impact on the development of these intentions later in life (Bein et al., 2023). With regard to the realisation of fertility intentions, Buber-Ennsner and Berghammer (2021) also found only small differences according to religiosity. Overall, similar patterns are observed across all European countries. Only Moldova stands out, as factors such as religiosity and union status are not or are less strongly related to the fertility intentions of young women. This finding suggests that children are of significant value to women across all socio-economic groups in Moldova.

This study is not without its limitations. First, the analyses do not permit conclusions to be drawn about any causal effects of socio-demographic characteristics on fertility gaps and the intended family size. The study's main focus is on the age-specific differences in various fertility indicators and gaps. Second, the use of a synthetic life course – by comparing different age groups – prevents the observation of changes over individual life courses. Consequently, cohort effects cannot be ruled out. Third, it is important to consider that crisis contexts, such as COVID-19 or inflation, may have influenced the cross-country comparison. This is due to the fact that the GGS-II was conducted in different years across countries, ranging from 2020 to 2023. Finally, the data used cannot account for the inherent uncertainties associated with fertility intentions and ideals. These concepts are deeply rooted in societal norms (Philipov & Bernardi, 2012) and the principles of bounded rationality (Simon, 1990), which have “to cope with an uncertain world” (Gigerenzer, 2021). Certain groups, particularly those with lower levels of education and first-generation migrants, may be underrepresented in the study due to their higher tendency to select the “don't know” response option, indicating less rational decision-making (Milewski & Mussino, 2019). It would be interesting to explore whether the share of individuals expressing uncertainty in their fertility intentions or ideals has increased in recent years. An increase in this share could also reflect a decline in actual fertility rates, if those who are uncertain about their fertility preferences tend to have lower aspirations for having children and/or a large family.

Up-to-date evidence on the extent of discrepancies between fertility ideals, intentions, and behaviour is highly relevant in countries with low fertility rates, as it provides insights into which individuals, at which life course stages, (do not) realise the family size they intend or desire. Comparing our results to previous research, we observed some longer-term changes in fertility intentions and fertility gaps. However, the intended number of children among young women in 2020-2023 remained relatively high. Nonetheless, the question of whether fertility intentions have declined in more recent years, or whether they will decline in the coming years, and whether the recent fertility decline will lead to a longer-term permanent drop, remains an open question. Overall, our study suggests that a significant gap persists between fertility preferences and realised fertility, a phenomenon that is evident even in later ages where the recuperation process is at work. This highlights the continued importance of family policies in providing parents with the requisite support and a sense of security to achieve their desired family size, with an early timing – as opposed to perpetual postponement – being decisive. Comprehensive family policies that encompass multiple pillars of support – time, financial assistance, and services – while maintaining stability are crucial for fostering individuals' perception of family support.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Jasmin Passet-Wittig for valuable feedback on an earlier draft of this manuscript. This paper uses data from the Generations and Gender Programme (www.ggp-i.org). The Generations and Gender Programme has received funding from the European Commission, its Consortium Board Members, and National Funding Bodies, which are gratefully acknowledged. The collection of GGS-II wave 1 data is co-financed ...

- in *Austria* by Federal Chancellery of Austria (Grant Number: GZ 2021-0.522.605) and Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research (Grant Number: GZ 2020-0.759.579).
- in *Czech Republic* by Technology Agency of the Czech Republic under the ETA Programme (project no. TL03000338).
- in *Denmark* by ROCKWOOL Foundation.
- in *Estonia* by Tallinna Ülikool/ Tallinn University.
- in *Finland* by Svenska Kulturfonden, Alli Paasikiven Säätiö, Väestöliitto ry.
- in *Germany* by German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (Grant Number 01UW2001A, 01UW2001B, 01UW2001C).
- in *Norway* by Ministry of Children and Families, Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs, Norwegian Research Council (Project number 300870).
- in *United Kingdom* by Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC), Grant Number ES/V012770/1.

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Appendix

Table A1: Descriptive statistics. Women aged 18-49.

	Germany	Austria	Netherlands	Czech Republic	Croatia	Estonia	Norway	Denmark	Finland	Moldova	United Kingdom
Age											
18-24	17.3%	14.5%	19.9%	16.9%	17.9%	14.9%	21.1%	26.1%	19.6%	18.3%	16.5%
25-29	14.7%	17.5%	13.9%	10.8%	15.5%	13.3%	15.3%	13.3%	12.1%	18.5%	19.4%
30-34	17.8%	15.2%	16.1%	16.2%	11.9%	18.0%	16.3%	14.6%	14.7%	22.1%	16.7%
35-39	18.0%	16.5%	17.6%	18.5%	15.3%	17.4%	15.5%	15.8%	18.8%	17.4%	16.8%
40-44	17.2%	16.5%	17.1%	17.9%	20.6%	17.3%	15.8%	16.1%	17.2%	14.0%	15.7%
45-49	15.1%	19.8%	15.4%	19.6%	18.8%	19.2%	16.0%	14.2%	17.6%	9.6%	14.9%
Mean age	34.31	35.01	34.03	35.26	34.96	35.27	33.56	32.71	34.62	32.73	33.94
Parity											
Childless	46.0%	42.5%	48.1%	35.1%	38.9%	30.3%	43.8%	48.5%	48.1%	21.0%	43.3%
1 child	20.2%	20.1%	13.5%	18.9%	19.4%	21.4%	14.1%	14.2%	13.8%	23.6%	20.1%
2 children	23.9%	26.6%	26.8%	34.6%	28.9%	30.9%	28.4%	25.9%	24.9%	36.5%	24.7%
3+ children	9.9%	10.8%	11.6%	11.4%	12.8%	17.4%	13.8%	11.4%	13.2%	19.0%	12.0%
Mean number of children	1.02	1.10	1.06	1.26	1.20	1.41	1.15	1.03	1.10	1.60	1.11
Intended number of children											
0 children	14.5%	12.2%	15.6%	8.4%	11.0%	6.5%	9.3%	13.3%	20.6%	3.8%	15.6%
1 child	17.1%	16.7%	10.1%	18.2%	14.2%	16.3%	10.5%	10.6%	12.4%	9.7%	13.0%
2 children	47.5%	50.4%	50.1%	52.0%	46.0%	44.8%	49.9%	47.0%	43.2%	45.2%	44.5%
3 children	15.9%	15.7%	18.3%	16.9%	21.4%	25.2%	23.9%	23.6%	17.6%	30.1%	19.1%
4+ children	5.1%	4.9%	5.9%	4.4%	7.4%	7.2%	6.4%	5.5%	6.2%	11.1%	7.9%
Mean intended number of children	1.82	1.88	1.91	1.92	2.05	2.14	2.09	1.99	1.82	2.40	1.98
Ideal number of children											
0 children	8.9%	5.9%	10.6%	3.9%	3.8%	4.1%	4.9%	7.1%	13.9%	0.4%	8.8%
1 child	8.3%	10.2%	5.3%	9.1%	7.9%	6.7%	4.5%	4.2%	5.9%	4.2%	6.1%
2 children	46.3%	55.0%	51.6%	59.1%	49.1%	46.9%	50.4%	48.5%	45.6%	45.3%	50.2%
3 children	24.4%	21.8%	23.2%	23.0%	30.0%	33.7%	31.0%	30.7%	24.3%	35.6%	23.2%
4+ children	12.1%	7.2%	9.5%	4.9%	9.3%	8.6%	9.2%	9.5%	10.4%	14.6%	11.8%
Mean ideal number of children	2.28	2.17	2.19	2.17	2.38	2.39	2.38	2.34	2.18	2.68	2.30
Education											
Low	14.9%	15.1%	10.9%	8.9%	6.0%	12.7%	5.0%	29.9%	13.9%	29.3%	9.8%
Medium	53.5%	46.4%	38.8%	67.7%	56.1%	40.4%	41.3%	27.8%	42.6%	47.5%	34.8%
High	29.4%	36.3%	49.3%	22.7%	37.2%	46.4%	53.4%	41.8%	43.1%	18.9%	54.4%
Missing	2.2%	2.2%	1.0%	0.7%	0.7%	0.5%	0.4%	0.5%	0.4%	4.4%	1.0%

	Germany	Austria	Netherlands	Czech Republic	Croatia	Estonia	Norway	Denmark	Finland	Moldova	United Kingdom
Making ends meet											
With difficulty	21.0%	32.4%	27.3%	39.5%	46.9%	26.4%	21.2%	17.6%	25.9%	67.2%	43.0%
Fairly easy	22.2%	27.2%	29.2%	31.3%	24.1%	29.2%	21.9%	20.5%	26.0%	11.2%	29.3%
Easily	41.9%	30.7%	30.1%	24.6%	18.9%	28.5%	42.1%	45.7%	38.2%	19.7%	17.9%
Missing	14.9%	9.8%	13.4	4.5%	10.1%	15.9%	14.9%	16.3%	9.9%	1.9%	9.8%
Union status											
Single	17.2%	18.3%	23.7%	20.1%	17.3%	18.7%	24.6%	28.1%	21.9%	19.6%	27.8%
Non-marital cohabitation	33.8%	35.1%	42.0%	41.7%	26.2%	42.6%	42.4%	32.5%	37.4%	18.0%	36.4%
Married	48.9%	46.4%	34.0%	38.2%	56.1%	38.6%	33.0%	39.4%	40.7%	62.4%	35.6%
Missing	0.1%	0.3%	0.4%	0.0%	0.5%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.2%
Ever married											
No	45.5%	46.5%	60.9%	54.6%	39.0%	53.5%	59.7%	54.3%	50.0%	30.6%	55.9%
Yes	54.4%	53.3%	38.7%	45.5%	60.5%	46.5%	40.3%	45.7%	50.0%	69.3%	43.9%
Missing	0.1%	0.3%	0.4%	0.0%	0.4%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.2%
Religiosity											
Low	40.3%	35.5%	54.4%	53.6%	15.0%	44.8%	52.5%	38.9%	44.4%	2.2%	56.1%
Medium	39.1%	47.0%	29.3%	31.0%	55.8%	33.6%	27.8%	24.0%	40.6%	66.1%	30.5%
High	5.3%	5.1%	3.4%	4.4%	16.7%	3.0%	3.4%	1.6%	5.3%	26.1%	3.9%
Missing	15.4%	12.4%	12.9%	11.1%	12.5%	18.6%	16.4%	35.5%	9.7%	5.6%	9.5%
Foreign born											
No	87.1%	74.1%	88.9%	96.8%	91.2%	95.4%	84.4%	89.4%	94.3%	98.0%	81.5%
Yes	12.7%	25.6%	11.0%	3.1%	8.7%	4.5%	15.5%	10.6%	5.6%	2.0%	18.4%
Missing	0.1%	0.4%	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%	0.0%	0.1%	0,0%	0.0%
Observations	9,533	2,634	2,410	1,794	2,256	2,806	1,922	3,420	1,224	2,234	2,713

Note: Weights adjust for various socio-demographic variables. Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, Denmark, Netherlands, Norway: age, sex, education, and region. Germany: age, sex, marital status, household size, employment status, education, migration background, population structure, place of residence (Western/Eastern Germany). Moldova: age and sex.

Source: GGS-II Germany (2021-2022), GGS-II Austria (2022-2023), GGS-II Netherlands (2022-2023), GGS-II Czech Republic (2020-2022), GGS-II Croatia (2023), GGS-II Estonia (2021-2022), GGS-II Norway (2020), GGS-II Denmark (2021), GGS-II Finland (2021-2022), GGS-II Moldova (2020), GGS-II United Kingdom (2022-2023).

Table A2: Coefficient estimates from Poisson regression models, robust standard errors, dependent variable: intended number of children. Women aged 18-29.

	Germany (n=2,961)	Austria (n=837)	Netherlands (n=791)	Czech Republic (n= 377)	Croatia (n=719)	Estonia (n=760)	Norway (n=694)	Denmark (n=1,350)	Finland (n=448)	Moldova (n=702)	United Kingdom (n=810)
Age	-0.022*** (0.004)	-0.009 (0.007)	-0.011 (0.007)	-0.001 (0.009)	-0.004 (0.011)	0.004 (0.006)	-0.010 (0.007)	-0.019*** (0.005)	-0.033** (0.012)	-0.003 (0.005)	-0.001 (0.008)
Education (Ref.: Medium)											
Low	-0.143** (0.048)	0.098 (0.107)	-0.042 (0.073)	0.151 (0.083)	-0.012 (0.286)	0.086 (0.077)	0.006 (0.081)	-0.128* (0.051)	-0.169 (0.126)	0.052 (0.035)	0.321* (0.154)
High	0.056** (0.020)	0.071 (0.038)	0.071 (0.041)	0.048 (0.057)	-0.023 (0.055)	-0.077* (0.037)	0.013 (0.040)	0.037 (0.030)	0.089 (0.076)	-0.022 (0.044)	-0.062 (0.048)
Missing	-0.020 (0.045)	-0.024 (0.140)	0.302 (0.189)	0.524*** (0.066)	0.140 (0.275)	0.077 (0.181)	-0.332 (0.700)	-0.527 (0.352)	-	-0.157* (0.079)	-0.484 (0.284)
Making ends meet (Ref.: Fairly easily)											
With difficulty	-0.005 (0.031)	-0.010 (0.046)	0.026 (0.048)	-0.130* (0.065)	0.006 (0.050)	-0.036 (0.047)	-0.027 (0.048)	-0.011 (0.042)	0.062 (0.083)	-0.020 (0.044)	0.058 (0.055)
Easily	0.018 (0.023)	-0.020 (0.043)	-0.008 (0.045)	-0.130* (0.053)	-0.004 (0.050)	-0.001 (0.044)	-0.017 (0.039)	-0.023 (0.032)	0.089 (0.071)	0.020 (0.054)	-0.031 (0.065)
Missing	0.027 (0.106)	-0.096 (0.083)	-0.091 (0.068)	-0.089 (0.109)	-0.190 (0.123)	0.047 (0.071)	-0.134 (0.088)	-0.005 (0.044)	0.227 (0.235)	-0.212 (0.108)	-0.089 (0.121)
Union status (Ref.: Married)											
Single	-0.209*** (0.032)	-0.145* (0.064)	-0.260*** (0.068)	-0.197** (0.073)	-0.376*** (0.073)	-0.335*** (0.059)	-0.153** (0.058)	-0.275*** (0.052)	-0.505*** (0.125)	-0.072 (0.045)	-0.208** (0.080)
Non-marital cohabitation	-0.128*** (0.023)	-0.097 (0.053)	-0.201*** (0.055)	-0.061 (0.052)	-0.207*** (0.061)	-0.134*** (0.040)	-0.090 (0.050)	-0.148** (0.046)	-0.214* (0.096)	-0.034 (0.042)	-0.079 (0.063)
Missing	-0.317 (0.221)	-1.336 (0.728)	-0.407 (0.333)	-	-0.299 (0.305)	-0.225*** (0.051)	-	-0.205** (0.070)	-	-0.105 (0.106)	0.429*** (0.078)
Religiosity (Ref.: Low)											
Medium	0.173*** (0.019)	0.160*** (0.039)	0.163*** (0.040)	0.072 (0.053)	0.415*** (0.080)	0.111** (0.039)	0.153*** (0.036)	0.067* (0.029)	0.296*** (0.059)	0.143 (0.125)	0.172*** (0.048)
High	0.302*** (0.050)	0.342*** (0.075)	0.391** (0.129)	0.625*** (0.167)	0.603*** (0.088)	0.323* (0.162)	0.305* (0.133)	0.308*** (0.074)	0.644*** (0.196)	0.121 (0.130)	0.415*** (0.121)
Missing	0.040 (0.103)	0.142 (0.081)	0.096 (0.064)	0.040 (0.067)	0.491*** (0.139)	0.078 (0.059)	0.100 (0.079)	-0.004 (0.032)	-0.096 (0.211)	0.172 (0.136)	0.185 (0.112)
Foreign born (Ref.: No)											
Yes	0.004 (0.034)	0.088 (0.050)	-0.111 (0.082)	-0.331* (0.141)	0.016 (0.081)	-0.192 (0.120)	-0.107 (0.059)	-0.129* (0.052)	0.012 (0.186)	0.085 (0.108)	-0.113 (0.080)
Missing	0.179 (0.109)	0.016 (0.150)	-	-	0.875*** (0.143)	-0.240*** (0.054)	-	0.412*** (0.042)	-	-	-

Source: GGS-II Germany (2021-2022), GGS-II Austria (2022-2023), GGS-II Netherlands (2022-2023), GGS-II Czech Republic (2020-2022), GGS-II Croatia (2023), GGS-II Estonia (2021-2022), GGS-II Norway (2020), GGS-II Denmark (2021), GGS-II Finland (2021-2022), GGS-II Moldova (2020), GGS-II United Kingdom (2022-2023). Significance levels: +p<0.1; *p<0.05; **p<0.01; ***p<0.001

Table A3: Coefficient estimates from linear regression models, robust standard errors, dependent variable: intended-actual fertility gap. Women aged 30-39.

	Germany (n=3,492)	Austria (n=833)	Netherlands (n=822)	Czech Republic (n=684)	Croatia (n=644)	Estonia (n=1,012)	Norway (n=601)	Denmark (n=994)	Finland (n=432)	Moldova (n=935)	United Kingdom (n=1,006)
Age	-0.120*** (0.004)	-0.114*** (0.008)	-0.148*** (0.010)	-0.081*** (0.009)	-0.129*** (0.014)	-0.096*** (0.008)	-0.111*** (0.010)	-0.136*** (0.009)	-0.078*** (0.012)	-0.080*** (0.012)	-0.116*** (0.009)
Education (Ref.: Medium)											
Low	-0.144 (0.079)	0.064 (0.125)	-0.011 (0.125)	-0.274*** (0.081)	-0.858*** (0.156)	-0.083 (0.110)	-0.406* (0.163)	0.144 (0.181)	-0.293 (0.190)	-0.077 (0.088)	-0.263 (0.148)
High	0.232*** (0.027)	0.217*** (0.059)	0.331*** (0.058)	0.168** (0.057)	0.276*** (0.082)	0.189*** (0.054)	0.131 (0.079)	0.247*** (0.069)	0.260** -0.078***	0.130 (0.075)	0.368*** (0.066)
Missing	0.102 (0.069)	0.507 (0.701)	0.393 (0.366)	0.470 (0.389)	-0.428 (0.240)	0.116 (0.304)	-0.304 (0.234)	-0.936** (0.301)	-	0.549*** (0.154)	-0.485*** (0.132)
Making ends meet (Ref.: Fairly easily)											
With difficulty	-0.058 (0.041)	-0.045 (0.067)	0.165* (0.076)	-0.019 (0.063)	-0.253* (0.100)	-0.085 (0.068)	0.077 (0.102)	-0.132 (0.087)	-0.051 (0.113)	-0.041 (0.094)	-0.027 (0.069)
Easily	0.018 (0.033)	0.133* (0.066)	0.078 (0.064)	0.047 (0.066)	-0.103 (0.119)	0.043 (0.062)	0.097 (0.076)	0.073 (0.065)	-0.027 (0.084)	0.058 (0.109)	0.039 (0.078)
Missing	-0.156 (0.139)	0.188 (0.220)	0.194 (0.145)	0.028 (0.143)	-0.181 (0.192)	-0.106 (0.096)	0.017 (0.149)	-0.028 (0.115)	0.182 (0.210)	0.214 (0.333)	0.229 (0.170)
Union status (Ref.: Married)											
Single	0.181*** (0.048)	0.448*** (0.098)	0.135 (0.091)	0.328*** (0.099)	0.190 (0.142)	0.328*** (0.079)	0.248* (0.101)	0.631*** (0.097)	0.200 (0.133)	0.429*** (0.106)	0.107 (0.091)
Non-marital cohabitation	0.394*** (0.030)	0.253*** (0.061)	0.124* (0.058)	0.346*** (0.059)	0.406*** (0.097)	0.248*** (0.052)	0.143* (0.062)	0.361*** (0.055)	0.424*** (0.076)	0.199 (0.122)	0.127* (0.064)
Missing	0.027 (0.653)	-0.377*** (0.082)	0.458 (0.579)	-	0.349 (0.302)	-0.238 (0.271)	-	-	-	-	1.090** (0.369)
Religiosity (Ref.: Low)											
Medium	0.103*** (0.028)	0.249*** (0.056)	0.063 (0.062)	0.176** (0.058)	0.300** (0.105)	0.142* (0.058)	0.051 (0.070)	-0.103 (0.064)	0.103 (0.075)	0.121 (0.271)	0.240*** (0.066)
High	0.213** (0.071)	0.299 (0.169)	0.023 (0.162)	0.327* (0.131)	0.353* (0.150)	0.308 (0.162)	0.204 (0.188)	-0.059 (0.185)	0.022 (0.146)	0.150 (0.278)	0.264 (0.193)
Missing	0.157 (0.135)	0.060 (0.137)	-0.066 (0.143)	0.100 (0.096)	0.352 (0.186)	-0.010 (0.088)	0.008 (0.124)	-0.075 (0.064)	-0.121 (0.179)	0.109 (0.298)	0.039 (0.171)
Foreign born (Ref.: No)											
Yes	0.083* (0.041)	0.238** (0.078)	0.227* (0.089)	-0.228* (0.090)	0.394* (0.179)	0.233 (0.143)	0.261** (0.087)	0.201** (0.076)	0.392 (0.258)	0.334 (0.222)	0.156 (0.081)
Missing	0.236 (0.193)	-0.646*** (0.136)	0.314 (0.493)	0.376*** (0.084)	0.625*** (0.114)	-	0.793*** (0.209)	-	-0.079 (0.175)	-	-0.697*** (0.069)

Source: GGS-II Germany (2021-2022), GGS-II Austria (2022-2023), GGS-II Netherlands (2022-2023), GGS-II Czech Republic (2020-2022), GGS-II Croatia (2023), GGS-II Estonia (2021-2022), GGS-II Norway (2020), GGS-II Denmark (2021), GGS-II Finland (2021-2022), GGS-II Moldova (2020), GGS-II United Kingdom (2022-2023). Significance levels: +p<0.1; *p<0.05; **p<0.01; ***p<0.001

Table A4: Coefficient estimates from linear regression models with robust standard errors, dependent variable: ideal-actual fertility gap. Women aged 40-49.

	Germany (n=3,074)	Austria (n=964)	Netherlands (n=797)	Czech Republic (n=733)	Croatia (n=893)	Estonia (n=1,034)	Norway (n=627)	Denmark (n=1,076)	Finland (n=344)	Moldova (n=597)	United Kingdom (n=897)
Age	0.009 (0.007)	0.022* (0.011)	-0.008 (0.013)	-0.016 (0.010)	0.017 (0.011)	0.003 (0.010)	0.003 (0.013)	-0.004 (0.010)	-0.002 (0.019)	0.017 (0.014)	0.001 (0.013)
Education (Ref.: Medium)											
Low	-0.102 (0.199)	-0.239* (0.112)	0.184 (0.182)	-0.111 (0.081)	-0.113 (0.159)	0.055 (0.130)	0.203 (0.264)	0.179 (0.239)	0.675 (0.899)	0.079 (0.093)	-0.158 (0.407)
High	0.142*** (0.039)	0.090 (0.067)	0.142* (0.068)	0.011 (0.064)	0.262*** (0.063)	0.189** (0.058)	0.062 (0.086)	0.035 (0.082)	0.177 (0.119)	0.031 (0.106)	0.079 (0.074)
Missing	0.095 (0.095)	-0.444 (0.335)	-0.088 (0.318)	-0.226** (0.078)	0.006 (0.368)	1.465 (0.957)	-0.538*** (0.138)	-0.619*** (0.163)	-0.416* (0.188)	0.276 (0.210)	0.429 (0.618)
Ever married (Ref.: No)											
Yes	-0.380*** (0.049)	-0.521*** (0.074)	-0.330*** (0.075)	-0.544*** (0.103)	-0.768*** (0.101)	-0.255*** (0.060)	-0.245** (0.080)	-0.627*** (0.073)	-0.300* (0.131)	-0.577*** (0.123)	-0.406*** (0.085)
Missing	-0.387 (0.388)	-0.222 (0.436)	-0.746*** (0.130)	- -	-0.806 (0.536)	- -	1.085*** (0.130)	- -	0.196 (0.139)	- -	1.595*** (0.376)
Religiosity (Ref.: Low)											
Medium	0.161*** (0.043)	0.050 (0.067)	0.185** (0.070)	0.132* (0.061)	0.256* (0.105)	0.065 (0.061)	0.173* (0.083)	0.018 (0.067)	0.137 (0.108)	0.412 (0.390)	0.076 (0.077)
High	0.260** (0.100)	0.440 (0.261)	0.581 (0.408)	0.088 (0.123)	0.306** (0.118)	0.170 (0.171)	-0.008 (0.115)	0.081 (0.219)	0.332 (0.256)	0.229 (0.395)	0.072 (0.261)
Missing	0.050 (0.057)	-0.032 (0.081)	0.290* (0.118)	0.135 (0.112)	0.144 (0.139)	-0.015 (0.078)	0.051 (0.114)	0.022 (0.070)	0.268 (0.222)	0.101 (0.434)	-0.039 (0.177)
Foreign born (Ref.: No)											
Yes	0.109 (0.057)	0.280*** (0.079)	0.105 (0.119)	0.175 (0.188)	-0.048 (0.105)	0.054 (0.123)	0.179 (0.105)	0.225 (0.125)	0.310 (0.281)	0.130 (0.228)	0.446*** (0.117)
Missing	- -	-0.153 (0.082)	- -	- -	- -	0.400 (0.628)	- -	-0.372*** (0.065)	- -	- -	- -

Source: GGS-II Germany (2021-2022), GGS-II Austria (2022-2023), GGS-II Netherlands (2022-2023), GGS-II Czech Republic (2020-2022), GGS-II Croatia (2023), GGS-II Estonia (2021-2022), GGS-II Norway (2020), GGS-II Denmark (2021), GGS-II Finland (2021-2022), GGS-II Moldova (2020), GGS-II United Kingdom (2022-2023).

Significance levels: +p<0.1; *p<0.05; **p<0.01; ***p<0.001